

APPENDIX D – PARTICIPANT CHARACTERIZATION FORM FOR DEVELOPERS AND END USERS

DEVELOPERS

Participant data

* Indicates a mandatory question

Full name *

Your answer

Age

Your answer

Education *

- High school
- Higher
- Postgraduate
- Master's degree
- Doctorate

Field of study *

Your answer

Position (professional activity) *

Your answer

Experience with Java programming *

Your answer

Do you have any knowledge of blockchain technology? *

- Yes
- No

END USERS

Participant data

Full name * Your answer

Age * Your answer

Education *

- High

- Higher
- Postgraduate
- Master's
- Doctorate

Have you used the SEI platform before? *

- Yes
- No